

DESIGN OF BOLTED COMPOSITE LAMINATES *A Special Purpose Finite Element Method of Solution*

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a special purpose finite element method of solution for design of multiple-fastener composite joints subjected to an arbitrary loading condition is presented. The stress analysis is carried out in two steps. In the first step (source analysis) the far field stress distribution in the laminate is determined, while in the second step (target analysis) a series of detailed stress analyses of regions containing a single bolt hole is performed to determine the stress distribution around the bolt holes. Far field stress distributions, obtained in the source analysis is automatically transferred to the boundaries of the target models. The failure analysis includes evaluation of the failure modes net-section and bearing according to simple point stress criteria. An experimental program was performed to generate data which was used to validate the target and failure analyses. Good agreement was found between experiment and model results.

1. INTRODUCTION

Owing to the practical significance of bolted structures stress and failure analyses of laminated composites containing bolt holes have been extensively studied in the literature. Most studies have concentrated on laminates containing a single bolt hole and subjected to uniaxial loads. However, bolted joints for advanced applications are usually of multiple-fastener type and the loading conditions are generally complex. Snyder et al. [1] give a comprehensive review of current composite bolted joint analysis programs used in industry today [1-10]. Since none of the existing programs can be used to analyze multiple-fastener joints subjected to an arbitrary loading condition, the objective of the present study was to develop such a program.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider the bolted joint shown in Figure 1. A composite plate (1) is bolted to another structural member (2) (metal or composite) by a number of fasteners oriented in a certain pattern. The composite plate is made from fiber reinforced composite material such as unidirectional plies. The plate is considered thin. Figure 2 shows an enlargement of a rectangular region of the composite plate containing a bolt hole. The hole radius, can be slightly larger than the bolt radius. As the structure is loaded, the plate moves and the bolts contract a portion of the holes. As the load is increased failure of the joint may occur in different modes. The problem is to predict the failure load of the composite plate. In this paper the failure modes net-section and bearing, two basic failure modes of bolted laminates, are taken into account.

3. STRESS ANALYSIS

3.1 General remarks

To evaluate failure of the bolted laminate, it is first required to determine the stresses in the vicinity of the bolt holes. The stress analysis is carried out in two steps. In the first analysis, called the source analysis, the far field stress distribution in the joint is determined, while in the second analysis, called the target analysis, a series of detailed stress analyses of regions containing a single bolt hole are carried out.

3.1.1 Source analysis

The joined members are modeled by 8-node Serendipity elements under the assumption of plane stress conditions. The bolt holes are not modeled. The plates are connected by means of linear elastic spring elements, which are given a representative stiffness. The FE-model is generated by a pre-processor. The geometry of the bolted structure, basic material properties, ply-orientation, and loading conditions are specified by the user. Alternatively, the basic material properties may be obtained from a data base, linked to the pre-processor. The elastic properties of the laminate is calculated according to classical laminate theory.

3.1.2 Target analysis

Stress distributions in the vicinity of the bolt holes are determined automatically by a series of detailed FE-analysis of regions containing a single bolt hole. The contact between the bolt and the laminate is taken into account by a penalty method [11]. Far field stress distributions of the source model are transferred to boundaries of the target models.

4. FAILURE ANALYSIS

4.1 General remarks

Basic failure modes of bolted composite laminates include net-section, bearing and shear-out. The distinction between failure modes is established by a number of parameters (listed without considering the order of importance): joint geometry, loading condition, material system, ply orientation, and lateral constraint. Shear-out failure occurs predominantly in bolted laminates where the distance from the hole to the edge of the laminate is short. Shear-out failure may also occur in highly orthotropic laminates. In this paper the failure modes net-section and bearing are taken into account. Shear-out failure will be included in a later version of the analysis program.

4.2 Net-section failure

A Point Stress Criterion (PSC) [12] is used to predict net-section failure. Net-section failure is evaluated in points around the hole circumference where fibers are oriented in the tangential direction of the hole. It is assumed that failure occurs in any of the points when the tangential stress at some characteristic distance away from the hole reaches the unnotched strength of the laminate in the direction considered. The PSC is a two parameter model, i.e. unnotched strength and characteristic distance. It should be emphasized that the characteristic distance is not a constant value but varies depending on material system and ply orientation. Both tensile- and compressive reacted net-section failure are considered. Hence, unnotched strengths (in tension and compression, respectively) in conjunction with characteristic dimensions (in tension and compression, respectively) are required to evaluate net-section failure according to the PSC.

The unnotched strengths in tension, σ_{ot} , and compression, σ_{oc} , respectively, are predicted from Equations (1) and (2):

$$\sigma_{ot} = E_{\varphi} \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{oc} = E_{\phi}\epsilon_{1c} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_{1t} and ϵ_{1c} are the allowable strains in tension and compression, respectively and E_{ϕ} is the elastic modulus in the ϕ -direction.

The characteristic distances in tension and compression (d_{ot} and d_{oc} , respectively) varies depending on the ply-orientation. Thus, d_{ot} and d_{oc} varies around the hole boundary since the ply orientation varies around the hole with respect to the tangential direction. Hence, it is required to determine d_o in all directions considered. It is assumed that the variation of d_o with ply-orientation can be characterized by the tangential stress concentration factor, K_T . Thus, the variation of d_o with K_T is determined experimentally from a few laminates of different ply orientation. The characteristic distance, d_o , of any other ply-orientation (direction) of the same material system may be interpolated from this information.

4.3 Bearing failure

A point stress approach, similar to the PSC, is used to predict bearing failure. Bearing failure is evaluated in a number of points along the loaded half of the hole circumference. It is assumed that failure occurs in any of the points when the radial compressive stress, σ_r , reaches the unnotched compressive strength of the laminate, σ_{or} , at some characteristic distance, r_c , away from the hole edge. The unnotched compressive strength is predicted from Equation (3):

$$\sigma_{or} = E_r\epsilon_{1c} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_{1c} is the allowable strain in compression, E_r is the radial elastic modulus in the considered direction. It is assumed that r_c is a material constant depending on the degree of lateral constraint.

5. VALIDATION OF TARGET AND FAILURE ANALYSES

5.1 Experimental procedure and results

An experimental program was performed to generate data which was used to validate the target and failure analyses. Specimens were fabricated from the toughened graphite/epoxy HTA7/6376 system from Ciba-Geigy. The geometry of the specimens and the ply orientations are shown in Figure 3. A quasi-isotropic ply orientation with a total of 24 plies was selected in this study ($[(\pm 45/0/90)_3]_{S24}$). The ply orientation is symmetric and balanced with respect to the mid surface. The basic lamina properties are presented in Table 1.

The loading fixture is shown schematically in Figure 4. The specimens were placed between two steel plates and fastened with a steel bolt. The tests were performed without lateral constraint. The ultimate failure load was measured directly.

The ultimate gross-section strain, ϵ_{gross} , was determined from:

$$\epsilon_{gross} = \frac{P}{E_x wt} \quad (4)$$

where P is the ultimate failure load, E_x , is Young's modulus in the x-direction (loading direction), w is the width and t is the laminate thickness. The results are presented in Table 2.

5.2 Predictions

A typical FE-model (distorted) of a specimen is shown in Figure 5. The orthotropic specimen and the bolt are modeled using 3-node triangular anisotropic membrane elements.

The characteristic distances of the failure modes net-section and bearing, respectively were calculated from experimental data from one specimen, which failed in net-section ($d = 10$ mm, $w = 20$ mm) and another specimen, which failed in bearing ($d = 10$ mm, $w = 40$ mm). The calculated distances are: 0.39 mm (d_{ot}) and 0.39 mm (r_c).

The predicted effect of the ratio of d/w on ϵ_{gross} is compared with experimental results in Figure 6. Good agreement was generally obtained between experimental data and predicted results. A d/w -ratio in the 0.4-0.5 interval is optimum.

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7. DETAILS OF THE COMPUTER CODE

The computer code has so far been developed for personal computers only. A CPU of type Intel 80286 and a "math co-processor" are required. The machine must operate under DOS version 3.0 or later, and be fully compatible with IBM AT or PS/2. To execute the program, at least 576 KByte of free RAM is requested. Due to the computer intensive nature of the finite element method, it is recommended to install the programs on a hard disk. This will take approximately 0.5 MByte of disk space (including reasonable sized data bases). The users in- and output files require additional space. The programs operate in text mode so no graphics adapter is necessary. However, if an adapter compatible with EGA or VGA available, it is possible to draw geometries, meshes, and deformed configurations on the screen. Further details on the codes are given in a users manual.

8. REFERENCES

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LIST OF TABLE SYMBOLS

Symbol	Definition
E_1	Young's modulus in the fiber direction
E_2	Young's modulus in the transverse direction
G_{12}	Shear modulus in 1-2 plane
ν_{12}	Poisson's ratio for transverse strain in the 2-direction when stressed in the 1-direction
d	hole diameter
w	specimen width
ϵ_{gross}	ultimate gross-section strain

Table 1. Lamina elastic properties of HTA7/6376 graphite/epoxy system

E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ν_{12}
(GPa)	(GPa)	(GPa)	
147	10	5.2	0.31

Table 2. Ultimate gross-section strain, ϵ_{gross} , of HTA7/6376 specimen

d	w	ϵ_{gross}
(mm)	(mm)	(%)
10	50	0.24
10	36	0.32
10	25	0.47
10	20	0.43
10	16	0.34
10	14	0.28

Figure 1. Multiple-bolted joint subjected to tensile and shear loads.

Figure 2. Rectangular region containing a bolt hole.

Figure 3. Test specimen geometry and ply orientation.

Figure 5. Typical FE-model of a specimen.

Figure 4. Schematic of loading fixture.

Figure 6. gross section strain as a function of d/w - comparison of model and experimental results.

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